

Weight Optimisation of Composite Yacht Structures

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ABSTRACT

In composite structures like yacht hulls, decks and bulkheads, it is common practise to apply a layer of chopped strand mat (CSM) in between layers of woven rovings or non-crimp fabrics (NCF's). The reason for this is the presumption that the CSM layer prevents delamination between the woven roving or NCF layers in case of impact or other severe loading conditions.

With the introduction of state-of-the-art design tools like Finite Element Modelling and closed mould production processes like vacuum infusion, the designs of the composite laminates in hulls and decks are becoming more and more optimised. Just the switch from hand lay-up to vacuum infusion has resulted in a weight reduction of 30% by achieving a much higher fibre volume content. The process also allows the uses of other materials like NCF's which are very hard to impregnate with hand lay-up. Additional weight reduction can be achieved by optimising the lay-up of the laminates. The reduction or even complete elimination of CSM can be fully justified from a static strength point of view. For instance in aerospace applications, no CSM layers are applied at all between woven roving layers. Weight reduction in yacht structures is favourable, since a lower structural weight allows for more balance weight which can be located near the bottom of the hull, thus lowering the centre of gravity and thereby improving the stability.

Research has been performed on laminates with a varying CSM thickness or reinforcement stacking sequence. All laminates are produced with a vacuum infusion process, resulting in a uniform laminate quality. A polyester resin system is used in all laminates. Impact test at several impact energy levels and ILSS test have been performed on the samples to quantify the sensitivity for delamination and other interlaminair failure modes. Conclusions are drawn with respect to the influence of CSM on the interlaminair properties.

KEYWORDS

Vacuum infusion; weight optimisation; composite ship structures; delamination; interlaminair failure

1. INTRODUCTION

The Dutch composite industry is quite advanced with respect to closed-moulding techniques. One of the forerunners in the development of the vacuum infusion technique was Conyplex BV in Medemblik, The Netherlands. With the help of the Centre of Lightweight Structures TUD-TNO, the

vacuum infusion process was introduced to produce the Contest 55, a 55 ft sailing yacht, see Figure 1 and reference 1. Nowadays, about 80% of all composite parts production is done vacuum infusion, and all new yachts are especially designed for this process. With the switch from hand lay-up to vacuum infusion, also new materials were selected. Chopped strand mat (CSM) is used a lot with hand lay-up since it is easy to impregnate, helps with a fast build-up of laminate thickness and is relatively cheap.

Figure 1: Infusion of a Contest 55 hull

In composite structures like yacht hulls, decks and bulkheads, it is common practise to apply a layer of CSM between layers of woven roving or non-crimp fabrics (NCF's). The reason for this is the presumption that the CSM layer prevents delamination between the woven roving or NCF layers in case of impact or other severe loading conditions.

With the introduction of state-of-the-art design tools like Finite Element Modelling and closed mould production processes like vacuum infusion, the designs of the composite laminates in hulls and decks are becoming more and more optimised. Just the switch from hand lay-up to vacuum infusion has resulted in a weight reduction of 30% by achieving a much higher fibre volume content. The process also allows the uses of materials like heavy NCF's which are very hard to impregnate with hand lay-up. Additional weight reduction can be achieved by optimising the lay-up of the laminates. The reduction or even complete elimination of CSM can be fully justified from a static strength point of view. For instance in aerospace applications, no CSM layers are applied at all between woven roving layers. Weight reduction in yacht structures is favourable, since a lower structural weight allows for more balance weight which can be located near the bottom of the hull, thus lowering the centre of gravity and thereby improving the stability. A project has been started to investigated the influence of CSM on the interlaminair properties.

Figure 2: Finite element model of a Contest 50 CS

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Several laminates will be produced with lay-ups of woven roving and CSM, where the weight of the CSM layers is varied. The resulting laminates will be tested for interlaminar properties by impact, ILSS and climbing drum peel testing.

2.1. MATERIALS

The laminates used consist of the following reinforcement materials, see Table 1.

	Name	Code	Supplier	Areal weight
1	Tissu Roving 800 S4 (111A)	Woven roving	Les Fils D'Auguste Chomarar France	780 gr/m ² (+/- 5%)
2	CSM-powder bound	CSM600	Mühlmeier GMBH & CO Germany	600 gr/m ² (+/- 5%)
3	CSM-powder bound	CSM450	Mühlmeier GMBH & CO Germany	450 gr/m ² (+/- 5%)
4	CSM-powder bound	CSM225	Mühlmeier GMBH & CO Germany	225 gr/m ² (+/- 5%)
5	CSM-powder bound	CSM100	Mühlmeier GMBH & CO Germany	100 gr/m ² (+/- 5%)
6	Glass veil-powder bound	CSM30	Mühlmeier GMBH & CO Germany	30 gr/m ² (+/- 5%)

Table 1: Reinforcement materials

The reinforcement materials have been impregnated using the polyester resin Norpol 720-010 produced by Reichold. This particular resin is a medium reactive isophthalic polyester resin, unaccelerated and non-thixotropic with good mechanical strength, impact strength in particular. The resin is cured using 0.5%, 1% and 1% by weight of Norpol accelerator 9802-P (1%Co.), Norpol peroxide no 1 and Norpol inhibitor 9854, respectively.

Different laminate thickness effects the results of ILSS as well as impact testing, see reference 2 and 3 respectively. Therefore 2 series of laminates with a comparable range of thickness were prepared 2.8-3.5 mm and 4.0-4.3 mm, respectively. Because of the unstable nature of the CSM reinforcement, which makes controlled laminating difficult, some variation in thickness occurred. The laminates were nominally of 50% fibre volume fraction. Laminates with the following lay-ups, consisting of alternating layers of CSM / glass veil and layers of woven roving, were prepared and tested, see Table 2.

#	Description	Weight (g/m ²)	Plate thickness (mm)
1	6 layers of woven roving with 5 layers of CSM30	7510	4.2
2	5 layers of woven roving with 4 layers of CSM30	6214	3.5
3	6 layers of woven roving with 5 layers of CSM100	7682	4.2
4	5 layers of woven roving with 4 layers of CSM100	6305	3.3
5	5 layers of woven roving with 4 layers of CSM225	7155	4.0
6	4 layers of woven roving with 3 layers of CSM225	5712	3.2
7	4 layers of woven roving with 3 layers of CSM450	6733	4.0
8	3 layers of woven roving with 2 layers of CSM450	4835	2.8
9	4 layers of woven roving with 3 layers of CSM600	7248	4.3
10	3 layers of woven roving with 2 layers of CSM600	5034	3.0
11	7 layers of woven roving	7571	4.0
12	6 layers of woven roving	6426	3.5

Table 2: Lay-ups

2.2. LAMINATE PREPARATION

The laminates were produced by the vacuum infusion process, see Figure 3. The lay-up of the different layers is done by hand on a horizontal flat mould onto which surface Ciba QV 5110 mould release is

coated as a release agent. Furthermore a nylon peel ply from Tygavac and a resin distribution fabric from Newbury Engineered Textiles have been applied. The laminates have been injected at a pressure of 50 mbar and cured at 600 mbar at a room temperature for 12 hours. The laminates were postcured at 60°C for 4 hours. Specimens were cut with a water-cooled diamond-surrounded circular saw from Sankyo with a diameter of 180 mm and a blade thickness of 1.2 mm.

Figure 3: Infusion of laminate

2.3. IMPACT TESTING

In the marine industry there are problems associated with impacts sustained during fabrication, for example the dropping of tools inside the hull or collisions whilst moving or turning modules during assembly. Also in service collisions may lead to impact damage, from regular minor impacts whilst docking, through striking of floating objects in the water, to collisions with other vessels and grounding.

A series of tests has been conducted to investigate low-velocity impact behaviour. A guided drop-weight impact test rig was used for the tests in this work. A controlled, repeatable impact is achieved by dropping a striker attached to a weight onto a sample in a defined manner at a prescribed impact energy level. During the impact, the resistive force exerted by the specimen on the striker is measured by a load cell as a function of time, and stored for subsequent display and analysis.

There are two main parts to the test rig, a tower where the weight falls onto the sample held below and the recording unit with the computer software system. The tower consists of a sample area, where the where the sample is clamped, and a column down which an impactor head attached to a weight falls onto the sample. Specimens of 100 mm × 100 mm were cut from panels of 625 mm × 500 mm using the diamond-surrounded circular saw. The specimens were clamped using a 'picture frame' clamp of dimensions 90 mm × 90 mm with the flat, mould side of the specimen facing down. The clamping force has been applied by tithing eight bolts at 30 Nm using a torque wrench. The tower is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Impact test set-up

An impactor with a spherical nose of 15 mm diameter and a weight of 2.24 kg was dropped at the centre of the specimen from a selected height and was captured after the first rebound. The drop height could be adjusted to achieve the desired impact velocity or incident kinetic energy. An experimental structure of eight increasing incident energy levels was selected. One repetition of each test was made. All the data were recorded by a computerised capture unit sampling at 1 MHz. With known mass and initial impact velocity (measured separately using a time counter triggered by a pair of photodiodes), two successive integration's of the force-time record provide the impactor velocity and displacement histories from which the force-displacement relationship and the absorbed energy history can be established. After impact, the damage of each specimen was inspected visually.

2.4. ILSS TESTING

Figure 5: Test set-up of the short beam test

The interlaminar shear strength is defined as the shear stress at rupture, where the plane fracture is located between the layers of reinforcement of a composite structure. To determine the apparent ILSS short beam shear tests were performed according to the specification ASTM D2344. Specimens were cut in two directions along the two weave structures: namely the weft and the warp directions. Typical test set-up is shown in Figure 5. The recommended ratios of support span and specimen length to thickness are 5 and 7, respectively. Specimens were cut using the diamond-surrounded circular saw. The loading nose, as well as the supports, has a diameter of 3 mm.

The ILSS was calculated according to the ASTM-standard:

$$\text{ILSS} = \frac{3P_{\max}}{4wh} (N / \text{mm}^2)$$

where P_{\max} is the applied maximum load when the interlaminar failure occurred, w and h are the specimen width and thickness, respectively.

2.5. PEEL TESTING

One of the reasons to apply CSM between layers of woven roving is the occurrence of ripping of one or multiple layers when applying a tensile load perpendicular to the surface of a laminate in case no CSM is used. To determine the peel resistance of the different lay-ups climbing drum peel tests have been performed according to the specification ASTM D1781. This method is used to determine comparative rather than fundamental measurements. A peeling apparatus, consisting of a flanged drum, flexible loading straps, and clamps for holding the test specimen is used, see Figure 6. The outside radius of the drum and the radius of the flange are 50 mm and 62.5 mm, respectively. The outer layer, which to peel, consists of one layer of woven roving. The outer layer has been injected at once together with the rest of the layers of the specimen. At both short ends of the specimen the outer layer has an overhang of at least 40 mm for clamping. The test specimen has a wide of 25 mm and a length of 250 mm. Specimens were cut using the diamond-surrounded circular saw. The average peel torque, T , was calculated according to the ASTM-standard:

The average peel torque, T , was calculated according to the ASTM-standard:

$$\bar{T} = [(r_0 - r_i)(F_p - F_0)] / W$$

Where r_0 is the radius of the flange including one half the thickness of loading straps, r_i is the radius of the drum plus the thickness of the layer being peeled, F_p is the average load required to bend and peel the layer plus the load required to overcome the resisting torque, F_0 is the load required to overcome the resisting torque and W the width of the specimen.

Figure 6: Assembly of peeling apparatus

3. RESULTS

The results are shown for both series of laminates with the comparable range of thickness. In Figures 7, 11 and 12 trends are shown of impact test related data of the damage area, the maximum deflection and the maximum force. The results of the ILSS and peel test are shown in tables 3 and 4, respectively.

3.1. IMPACT TEST

The laminates have been tested on impact with various impact energies. The resulting damaged areas are measured and plotted in Figure 7. The trend lines shown are linear. The R^2 values indicate a 'goodness of fit', where a value of one means a perfect fit, that is that all of the data points are on one line.

Figure 7: Damaged area vs. impact energy

The damage sustained by the specimens may be roughly categorised into front- and backface bending damage and in general roughly circular internal shear delamination at lower incident energy levels. At higher energy levels these damage areas became asymmetric. Typical failure modes include matrix cracking, surface microbuckling, delamination, fibre shear-out and fibre fracture. Examples of the front- and backface of the damage sustained by specimens subjected to low and high incident energy levels are shown in Figure 8, respectively.

Figure 8: Damage at low impact energy (left) and high impact energy (right), top view

Figure 9: Damage at low impact energy (left) and high impact energy (right), bottom view

The mid-plane delamination was generally seen to have the largest area of the damage mechanisms, and where possible it was this area that was measured. The damage areas were measured visually. It is thought that the measured values were sufficiently accurate to allow comparisons to be made. There does not to be any damage threshold below which no damage is seen, as reported for higher fibre volume fraction glass polyester laminates by Zhou, see reference 4. Even for the lowest incident energies used here, an area of internal delamination was measured. Maybe the use of an impactor with a spherical nose caused a small contact area leading to high shear and normal stresses. In particular on the thinner specimens some damage also occurred at higher impact energy at the edges of the specimens, where they were clamped between the steel plates of the test tower. As mentioned by Sutherland and Guedes Soares, see reference 5, the asymmetric nature of the damage of some specimens lead to the hypothesis that some slippage was occurring at the higher impact energies where the specimens were clamped. The irregular surface of the non-mould side of the specimens, together with the low friction between the steel clamp and polyester resin would make slippage feasible at the highest impact energy levels.

To compare the different laminates, a typical impact energy of 15 joules is selected. The damaged area for all laminates is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Damaged area for all laminates with 15 joules impact energy

For the thinner laminates adding CSM-30 gr/m2 results in a significant smaller damage area in comparison to the laminate laid-up only with woven-roving. Further raising the weight of CSM to 100 or 225 gr/m2 did not influence the size of the damaged area. Only at 450 gr/m2 the damage area is reduced even further. At 600 gr/m2 the trend line moved up again indicating a decreasing impact damage resistance. The size of the damaged areas of the thicker laminates are bigger in comparison to those of the thinner laminates. However the effect of adding CSM on damage resistance for thicker laminates is not unequivocal.

During testing, the maximum deflection of the specimen as well as the impact force are also computed. As would be expected the displacement of the thinner, more flexible laminates are larger and the impact force experienced by the specimens will be lower compared to the thicker, stiffer laminates, as is shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12 respectively.

Figure 11: Maximum deflection for laminates with different thickness

Figure 12: Maximum force for laminates with different thickness

The resulting data related to maximum deflection and maximum force of the other laminates showed similar values as the ones shown in the figures above.

3.2. ILSS TEST

Specimens with a width-to-thickness ratio b/t of 1 were tested for the warp and weft direction. The results from the ILSS tests are summarised in table 3.

Laminate	Warp		Weft		t (mm)
	ILSS (N/mm ²)	St. Dev. (N/mm ²)	ILSS (N/mm ²)	St. Dev. (N/mm ²)	
Woven roving	25.17	0.76	23.25	0.64	3.5
Woven roving+CSM30	28.06	0.15	24.67	0.91	3.5
Woven roving+CSM100	24.74	1.07	25.26	0.68	3.3
Woven roving+CSM225	24.67	1.57	24.85	0.70	3.2
Woven roving+CSM450	23.69	1.41	21.33	1.86	2.8
Woven roving+CSM600	26.27	1.50	24.59	2.52	3.0
Woven roving	27.26	1.27	25.98	0.55	4.0
Woven roving+CSM30	28.29	2.18	26.39	1.42	4.2
Woven roving+CSM100	27.23	1.15	26.37	0.96	4.2
Woven roving+CSM225	25.51	1.21	27.04	1.32	4.0
Woven roving+CSM450	23.72	0.41	22.15	0.35	4.0
Woven roving+CSM600	27.49	1.37	27.72	0.75	4.3

Table 3: Results ILLS test

Laminates laid up with layers of woven roving and CSM-30 gr/m² result in a higher interlaminar shear strength in comparison to laminates of comparable thickness but laid-up only with woven roving. ILSS values decrease when adding thicker and heavier layers of CSM up to 450 gr/m² even below the original value of the laminate laid-up of only woven-roving. When adding more CSM (600 gr/m²), ILSS values will increase again. This trend can be seen in warp direction as well as in weft direction, although in general ILSS values in weft direction are smaller compared to those in warp direction. This may be caused by the twill weave pattern of the woven roving.

3.3. PEEL TEST

The results from the peel tests are summarised in table 4.

Description	Average peel torque (mmN/mm)	St. Dev. (mmN/mm)
Woven roving	29.06	1.42
Woven roving+CSM30	21.87	2.17
Woven roving+CSM100	20.05	1.25
Woven roving+CSM225	not yet tested	
Woven roving+CSM450	not yet tested	
Woven roving+CSM600	20.62	1.38

Table 4: Results peel test

The average peel torque value of the laminate without the use of CSM exceeds those with the use of CSM by far. Furthermore the test results indicate that no difference in average peel torque is made when using different amounts of CSM. The specimens were inspected visually to determine the nature of failure. The fibres of the layers peeled off from the laminates using CSM are, examined visually, free of resin. This indicates that the interface between fibre and resin dominated the failure mode.

Perhaps the powder used for binding the CSM or the sizing of the CSM fibres weakens the interfacial bond between fibre and resin.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A large number of specimens were subjected to impact, ILSS and climbing drum peel testing. Results have been presented for damage area, maximum deflection and maximum force for specimens subjected to impact at different energy levels. Also the values of interlaminar shear strength as well as the average peel torque have been presented.

For the thinner laminates the size of the damaged area of specimens subjected to impact were reduced by adding layers of CSM between the layers of woven-roving. Adding more weight of CSM will not lead to a proportional raise of impact resistance expressed in a proportional smaller sized damaged area. At equal energy levels bigger damaged areas occurred at the thicker specimens in comparison to the thinner specimens. Adding CSM did not result in any major changes in the size of the damaged area for any of the thicker laminates. As expected the thicker laminates experienced a smaller maximum deflection and a higher maximum impact force compared to the thin laminates.

The ILSS values were higher for laminates with CSM of 30 gr/m² in comparison to laminates laid-up only with woven-roving. Adding more weight of CSM reduced these values again. However at 600 gr/m² the ILSS values of the same level of the laminates with CSM of 30 gr/m² were reached again. This trend was seen for the thinner as well as the thicker laminates.

The average peel torque required to peel of one layer was reduced by adding layers of CSM. Perhaps this has been caused by the sizing agent or the powder used for binding the fibres of the CSM cloth.

The tests performed for this research program indicated the use of layers of CSM has been beneficial to the damage resistance of the laminates in case of some severe loading conditions. Weight optimisation can be achieved by using CSM cloth with a low areal weight, since these laminates generally gave the best results in relation to damage resistance.

Although a considerable number of specimens were tested much more work has still to be done. This work can be seen as a first step of a more extensive research program. More laminates with other lay-ups and stacking sequences have to be made and tested. Furthermore the effect of impact damage on the residual compressive strength has to be investigated. To be able to set up a predictive model of the mechanical properties and damage resistance of laminates more research and the use of a finite element analysis based computer program is necessary.

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